

AIAL's Comments to the European Commission's Digital Fairness Act Consultation

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ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

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1. Introduction

This document represents the answers prepared by the team at AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) for the *European Commission's Digital Fairness Act Consultation*¹, conducted by the European Commission as part of the lawmaking process. The consultation was open from 17th July until 24th October 2025, during which the AIAL team submitted its response.

The Digital Fairness Act represents a landmark regulation as it directly addresses key misgivings about the experiences of consumers online. The comments provided by the AIAL are based on its findings established through research, analysis of the current realities, and a careful assessment of practical feasibility. We hope the Commission will find our recommendations useful and pragmatic, and are available to engage further on these as well as other measures to support the EU's implementation of regulations as instruments for upholding our fundamental rights.

In light of the current discussions surrounding simplification, we request the Commission to investigate measures that reduce the effort of enforcement by supporting organisations with their compliance instead of focusing on reduction or dilution of regulations. For the Digital Fairness Act, this means ensuring a high-degree of consumer protection, as required by the Charter of Fundamental Rights, is provided through the regulation with simplification via supporting resources and procedures rather than dilution. Indeed, we feel that the EU can and should utilise its highly valued rights and freedoms as the very measures for measuring competitiveness and innovation, rather than focusing only on the artificially amalgamated metrics regarding its economy. We reiterate that a healthy and competitive EU is one where the competition comes from a high degree of assurance and accountability, and not where such measures can be easily sidelined for economic reasons.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14622-Digital-Fairness-Act>

2. Transparency of Contracts

Consumers increasingly use online services and have difficulty in understanding their contractual terms and its implications due to their length, complex language, and structure. Despite regulations encouraging the establishment of simple language, the reality is that consumers face a difficult time as they do not understand their contracts, are forced to accept whatever is provided to them, and most importantly – they cannot go back and see what they agreed to. This should be fixed by the DFA through specific measures which we outline below as recommendations.

Recommendation 2.1: *When consumers are offered contractual terms as part of a digital interface involving multiple layers, pages, or other fragmented means, the consumer has the right to also obtain the same contract in a single-page or a single-document form.*

Recommendation 2.2: *When consumers agree to specific contractual terms, the consumer has the right to access those same contractual terms at any later date. If the contractual terms are provided through an online interface or a website, and the terms on such interfaces have changed from the perspective of the consumer, the service provider must clearly provide the consumer with information on where to find the specific version and text of the contractual terms that were agreed by the consumer.*

Recommendation 2.3: *When the subject matter of contract concerns the provision of an online service or an otherwise predominantly digital service, the contract must state the nature of the service in a clear and comprehensible manner such that the consumer is able to identify and understand the service as covered by the contract. The contract must also specifically list the features and functionalities provided as part of that service. Where such features and functionalities have a significant change, this must be taken as a change in the contractual terms, and the consumer must be made aware of such changes in order to make an informed decision to continue.*

3. Fairness in Contracts

The rise of services provided via the internet has also increased the use of standard form contracts which are drafted by the service provider and where the consumer has no choice but to accept or reject them. The Unfair Commercial Practices Directive references this as one of the necessities for establishing unfair contractual terms as a means to protect the consumer from their ill-effects. The DFA, as a natural progression of consumer protection law after the Directive, should further strengthen the definition and categorisation of unfair terms in a way that is relevant to the modern digital ecosystem. For this, we provide the below recommendations.

Consumers agree to the use of a "service" within online contracts. However, after acceptance, the consumer has no information about the service in terms of how it

works, what is covered or what is not, what to expect in terms of performance, changes, and other considerations. The consumer is thus left at the mercy of the service provider to receive any service that is being given without any evidence that would allow them to claim how and where the service is not being provided. For example, when accessing an online video streaming service, if the consumer has no information on how many videos they can watch or where, or other aspects regarding performance (e.g. video quality), then they cannot later assess whether they are receiving the service they paid for. In contrast, consider the regulated services such as telecoms where they know how many voice call minutes or data they can use. In such cases, the consumer also knows that they can rely on the service based on these parameters, as otherwise the consumer may be required to make adjustments to their use if the service suddenly changes.

Recommendation 3.1: *Contracts which concern the use of a service by the consumer must provide sufficient information for the consumer to measure and establish the quality and stability of the service being provided. Contracts that do not provide this information must be considered as unfair.*

4. Consumer Rights

Consumers who access a service may lose such access due to alleged infringements or violation of policies. It is a common experience for online platforms to not inform the consumer of the exact nature of the infringement or violation, which means the consumer does not have a specific idea or reference to a clause which legally informs them why their contractual basis has been terminated. Appeals are difficult as consumers are stuck handling automated interfaces or must wait indefinitely for a resolution. The DFA should address this disparity between consumer rights and the service provider's ability to deny the consumer without meaningful recourse.

Recommendation 4.1: *When a consumer is denied access or use of a service due to a violation of a contractual term or policy, the service provider must inform the consumer, at minimum, which specific aspect of the policy or prohibition has been infringed, and whether this was determined entirely algorithmically or through a human review. Where such decisions are taken entirely algorithmically, they should be considered as legal effects in light of the GDPR's obligations regarding automated decision making. The obligation to provide information regarding service denial should be considered an absolute right of the consumer and should not be exempted for cases such as fraud prevention or trade secrets as doing so will leave the consumer unable to understand their expulsion as well as from exercising their consumer rights in relation to appeals, redress, or complaints.*

5. Emerging Consumer Risks in AI Services

We define an "AI Service" as a service whose primary benefit is the provision of a particular AI technology to the consumer. Examples of this are ChatGPT, Midjourney, Google Gemini, Microsoft Co-Pilot, and others. Typically, such AI services include the use of an "AI model" that is a large language model (LLM), which then is used in various ways to provide generation or manipulation of content in the form of a service. Such models have a large capacity to create risks, with the AI Act defining this capacity as "systemic risk" and regulating it specifically to avoid harms to the rights and freedoms of individuals. While the AI Act has already been published and is on track to be enforced, we envision the DFA to provide additional protections and safeguards to consumers of such AI services for the following concerns which are currently not covered by the AI Act or other consumer protection laws such as the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive.

As AI technologies are fairly new in terms of their rapid progress and the development and adoption of the AI Act as a specific law that regulates them, consumers will not be aware of the legal implications when using AI services. In our survey of common terms offered by AI service providers, we find disturbing clauses where the terms list several requirements or prohibitions with a "get away" clause such as "unless allowed /restricted by applicable laws". Such phrases are not clear to consumers as the knowledge of all possible laws and their interpretations cannot be reasonably expected from a general well-informed consumer.

Recommendation 5.1: *Contracts permitting or restricting activities or the use of a service should reiterate, explicitly, what laws are applicable, the specific rights available to the consumer, and how to exercise them. Contracts that do not provide this information and instead list practices with the obligation on the consumer to identify whether they are permitted or prohibited under applicable laws should be considered unfair as the consumer cannot be reasonably expected to undertake such a legal exercise and also is not involved in the drafting of the contract.*

Some AI services such as Deepseek claim to not support the jurisdiction of the EU but still permit consumers from the EU to access and use the service. Since consumers expect the terms they agree to have relevant consumer protection as per EU law, this creates an environment where AI service providers are able to exploit EU consumers without adherence to the EU's strict regulations. Such practices should be banned, and the consumers must be informed that their terms are invalid as the services are not supported within the EU. In order to enforce this, the competent authorities must also be empowered to prohibit or remove the service from the EU market until it establishes its compliance.

Recommendation 5.2: *For services not established in the EU, offering contracts to the EU consumers in a way that attempts to mislead the consumers into thinking the service respects EU laws, or by making the consumers accept the laws of another non-aligned jurisdiction without acceptance of EU laws, must be considered as unfair and illegal. Competent authorities must have the power to ban such services or to stop their use by consumers until the service providers demonstrate with sufficient implementations that they support the requirements of relevant EU laws.*

The rise of AI service providers, which includes numerous websites and apps offering custom AI services based on offerings of large AI providers, also creates specific risks for consumers due to the loss of data in the use of such services. For example, the terms of AI services often include clauses that restrict the rights of the consumer over the data they provide for use of AI service (e.g. text prompts to ChatGPT or Deepseek). Such restrictions can take the form of transfer of rights, granting irrevocable license to use the data in any way the service provider sees fit, or to indicate that the consumer is willingly donating this data without restrictions. Additionally, the AI service terms also indicate that the liability for ensuring the inputs are adherent to relevant copyright, IP, and data protection laws, which means the user takes the liability for using the service by providing free data to the service provider. This should be clearly understood to be unfair. The same also occurs in the context of outputs i.e. data generated by the AI services, where the consumer again assumes all responsibility and liability. For example, if the consumer enters a prompt to generate a specific text, image, or video content, then the terms indicate that the consumer is liable if this content violates their policies or any laws. This is despite the consumer only having the capacity to provide input, and where the consumer has no control or role in the development and functioning of the AI model or service. Thus, such terms should be considered unfair as they attempt to shift the responsibilities from the AI service to the consumers who are forced to accept such contracts and are not even aware of having taken on such responsibilities.

Recommendation 5.3: *Where contractual terms concern the use of services, the following are considered as unfair:*

1. *The shifting of liability from the service provider to the consumer when the consumer does not control the development or functioning of the service;*
2. *The transfer of rights related to the data provided as part of using the service beyond those strictly necessary to use the service;*
3. *The shifting of liability or responsibility to a consumer regarding the outputs produced by a service when the consumer only has the option to provide inputs to the service and does not have a material influence or control over how the outputs are generated from the inputs;*

4. *Assigning to the consumer any responsibility that would result in a violation or infringement of a policy, terms, or a legal obligation where the consumer does not have the capacity to determine when such infringements might occur, or to change them after occurring, or where such responsibilities would have been assigned to the service provider in absence of the consumer.*

When consumers use AI services, the outputs they receive are based on the specific AI model that is being used by the service. When this model is changed, the nature of the entire service changes as it now provides completely different outputs for the same inputs, and also behaves in different ways regarding safety, precluded contents, and preferring specific outputs over others. For the consumer who has agreed to the use of a specific service, the use of another model without a notice or control represents a significant change in the service as the new model works differently from what they expect. If the consumer were using the service for specific tasks, the implementation of those tasks will now be affected, and the consumer may have to expend considerable effort to understand what has changed, whether it is for the better, and whether they should make further changes to their workflows in order to ensure their tasks are completed in a satisfactory manner. The consumer may also want to revert back to the specific AI model that was in use before so that their current tasks continue while they investigate the potential of the new model.

While we understand that the service provider has the prerogative to decide which service to be provided and how, we also point to the nature of a contractual relationship as being one of assurance regarding what the consumer can expect from the service provider. By changing the service in this manner, i.e. without notice and without adequate time or controls, the service provider risks causing mental distress and potential economic harm to the consumer who relies on the service. To remedy this, the DFA must ensure that changes to the service, especially regarding AI models, must be performed without affecting the interests and rights of the consumers.

Recommendation 5.4: *Where consumers have a contractual relationship with an AI service provider, significant changes to the AI service, including where changes to the underlying AI model results in significant changes to the consumer's experience of using the service, must not be made without notifying the consumer in advance. If such significant changes are expected to affect the consumer in terms of relying on the use of the service, the consumer must be provided sufficient time and controls to manage the change without disruption to their existing use of the service.*

AI service providers also frequently limit the use of the service in terms of how the consumer can further utilise the outputs generated. For example, the terms would have a clause that prohibits the use of output for being used by the consumer to train other models. Such restrictions are incompatible with situations where the consumer pays for the use of the service, and consequently for the generation of the output. By

limiting where and how the consumer can further use such outputs in respect of training other AI models, even in a personal capacity, is a tactic that would fall under anti-trust measures when done at large scale. At the same time, the terms also permit the AI service providers to retain the outputs for further use in their own activities, including in the training or refinement of their AI models. As the rights and capabilities granted to the consumer are entirely out of balance compared to those of the service provider, and in context of the consumer paying for use of the service, this should represent an unfair contract as it exploits the consumer by limiting their ability to make effective use of the service.

Recommendation 5.5: *The use of contracts or policies to limit the use of AI generated content outside the service is considered unfair if the consumer is paying for the generation of said content through the service and has the responsibility or liability associated with it. If the service provider retains responsibility and liability for the generated content, it may stipulate that the consumer may not use the content outside of the specified service for commercial activities.*

The conversational nature of LLMs allows people to phrase questions, interact in different ways, and even engage in discussions. This represents a serious psychological risk where the consumer may get addicted, may experience phobias, false beliefs, and may even end up believing the AI is becoming sentient. These risks can also create suicidal tendencies, promote or encourage self-harm, and confirm inherent biases and discontention already being experienced by the consumer. These are not hypotheticals but realities.² Additionally, most AI services are powered by a handful AI models that are developed by a small group of companies. The control of these companies over the models extends to what values they encode, how they respond, and what kind of content is being permitted to be included or generated. For example, certain AI model providers have been documented to explicitly permit statements that demean people based on "protected characteristics", or in simple terms to allow racist, homophobic, or other kinds of unacceptable content.³ These same "guidelines" have also permitted engaging in romantic or "sensual" conversations with children. Not only are these practices harmful to a significant vulnerable section of the society, they also risk creating disharmony and encouraging discontent. The intimate nature of conversations

² A teen contemplating suicide turned to a chatbot. Is it liable for her death?: A lawsuit filed by the parents of 13-year-old Juliana Peralta is the third high-profile case to allege an AI chatbot contributed to a teen's death by suicide. (Washington Post, 2025) <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2025/09/16/character-ai-suicide-lawsuit-new-juliana/>

³ Meta's AI rules have let bots hold 'sensual' chats with kids, offer false medical info: An internal Meta policy document, seen by Reuters, reveals the social-media giant's rules for chatbots, which have permitted provocative behavior on topics including sex, race and celebrities. (Reuters, 2025) <https://www.reuters.com/investigates/special-report/meta-ai-chatbot-guidelines/>

also creates opportunities for such companies to exploit the emotional state and vulnerabilities of their users to target ads.⁴

There is a growing category of apps where AI is used intentionally to form relationships with the users. Such apps are called "Companion Apps" and are widely popular on platforms like iOS, Android, and are accessible through a web browser. Examples of popular companion apps include Replika, Nomi, [Character.ai](#), and others. Such apps pose a significant risk to their users, who as consumers not only risk forming emotional bonds that can be exploited, but also act as mechanisms for new kinds of dark patterns that draw on the vulnerabilities and the intimate nature of conversations. The apps also are a risk in terms of inducing the users to share more data or to purchase more "outfits" or "dialogues" for the companions in a way that compels the individual based on the effect of the established emotional relationship. Of immediate concern, some companion apps are pitched as regulated professions such as therapists and doctors but without the assurances or professional qualifications or liabilities. We therefore urge the DFA to also address these growing risks of companion apps as new means of consumer relationships (both literal and contractual), and where we foresee a necessity to undertake impact assessments to evaluate whether certain practices should be categorised as high-risk or unfair.

Recommendation 5.6: *The DFA should establish an annex listing specific categories of consumer interactions or relationships as being high-risk, with additional protections and rights. The activities listed in the annex should be updated through delegated acts, similar to the model implemented within the AI Act. In particular, the annex within the DFA should provide categorisations based on the nature of the underlying service, the ability of the individual to participate in the contract-forming process i.e. whether it is negotiated or not, and the inherent risk to the consumer in the use of the service (such as for companion apps). The DFA should provide, as part of future rule making process, the framework for impact assessments to be carried out for such high-risk activities with a view towards potential certification or auditing necessities in the near future.*

6. Support Consumers in Managing Digital Privacy

We support the Commission's agenda for streamlining online experiences for consumers by directly addressing concerns such as dark patterns and misleading practices. We propose that the Digital Fairness Act (DFA) also addresses two key issues that impact the consumer's fundamental rights – namely the consent fatigue caused by incessant invalid consent popups , and the large-scale, invasive, and uncontrolled sharing of personal data to thousands of data brokers in the name of

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Meta whistleblower Sarah Wynn-Williams says company targeted ads at teens based on their 'emotional state' (TechCrunch, 2025)
<https://techcrunch.com/2025/04/09/meta-whistleblower-sarah-wynn-williams-says-company-targeted-ads-at-teens-based-on-their-emotional-state/>

"necessary-for-business advertising". To remedy this, we advocate consideration of three key measures:

1. Safeguard the privacy of consumers in online and digital services;
2. Develop a technical framework to support privacy and consumer protection;
3. Empower consumers to formulate their own contractual terms that are then enforced by their "digital agents"

6.1 Safeguard privacy of consumers in online and digital services

The processing of personal data is already subject to the strict requirements imposed by the GDPR. However, when data subjects are also acting as consumers, their processing should also benefit from the additional rights and restrictions that are afforded to them through the right to consumer protection. To ensure this occurs, and there is no fragmentation of experience and enforcement for consumers across the GDPR and the DGA, the drafting of the DFA should explicitly align its intended effects with those from the GDPR in terms of rights, obligations, and necessity to ensure fundamental rights.

Recommendation 6.1.1: *The DFA should have an explicit acknowledgement and clarification regarding the rights of the consumer when they are also a data subject under the GDPR for the same contractual terms or service. The clarification should include the validity of contracts, especially when such contracts are unfair, with respect to the use of contract performance as a legal basis under the GDPR.*

A consumer protected by the DFA, and who is also a data subject under the GDPR, would benefit from the obligations imposed by the DFA regarding contractual terms. However, GDPR also defines two other legal bases – namely consent and legitimate interests - which are relevant to the experiences of the consumer and their ability to access and use the services, as well as how their personal data is processed and shared elsewhere. A consumer thus protected regarding fairness of contractual terms would still be susceptible to the misuses of consent and legitimate interests. While such misuses are already addressed by the GDPR, for example by assessing the validity of consent, for consumers this represents a fracturing of the safeguards. For example, an individual protected as a consumer when forming a contract should not lose that protections after this step just because they are now consenting or being informed about the use of legitimate interests. Therefore, the principle of consumer protection should also be extended to all interactions and activities where the individual continues to be a consumer, and where the subject matter of the contract is in effect. This will allow the use of consent and legitimate interests on the personal data of the consumer, to be aligned with the protections, safeguards, and fairness that the consumer benefits from through the DFA's focus on unfair terms. Such explicit

alignments will support harmonisation of the GDPR's implementations with that of contracts, and thereby combine the fundamental rights of privacy and data protection with those regarding consumer protection.

Recommendation 6.1.2: *The DFA should address the expectations of the consumer in terms of other legal bases such as legitimate interests and consent, which occur in their interactions as a consumer and under a relationship established by a contract. Where such extra-contractual legal bases are intended to deceive, manipulate, or mislead the consumer, the use of the contractual relationship in this manner should be considered as being an unfair and unbalanced to the detriment of the consumer.*

With regards to the privacy of consumers, it cannot be expected that consumers will understand the nuances of the law and the differences in implementation of consumer protection, privacy, and data protection as three separate regimes within the EU's complex legal framework. When an individual establishes a relationship as a consumer, it should be considered as within the consumer's expectations to have all relevant rights afforded to them, whether as a consumer or data subject, be provided by the service provider without distinguishing their origin in law. Therefore, we request the DFA to consolidate such rights from the GDPR and other legal mechanisms under the umbrella of consumer rights when the primary relationship between a consumer and the relevant rights provider or implementor is based on a contract. This will allow consumers access to the relevant information in a single place (their contract) and will also ensure that the existence and implementation of GDPR rights is afforded an additional measure of enforcement through contract law.

Recommendation 6.1.3: *The DFA should establish that where a consumer is also a data subject under the GDPR for the same services or contractual terms, their rights under the GDPR must be considered as part of their consumer rights and be established as such in their contractual terms.*

Consumers are increasingly utilising services, devices, applications, and other interfaces in digital forms and with internet connectivity. The proliferation of internet and digital technology has created a vast net that harvests personal data in unprecedented forms. For consumers, this results in an inability to control their privacy and experiences, and thus also affects their ability to understand, agree, and utilise a service in a fair manner. We therefore request the DFA to address consumer privacy as a topic with urgency as part of the broader remit of consumer protection.

Recommendation 6.1.4: *The DFA should establish the consumer's right to a high degree of privacy as part of their right to consumer protection. This right must be implemented in accordance with the GDPR, specifically through the principles of transparency,*

purpose limitation, data minimisation, and the necessity for the consumers to be provided with the ability to consent or object (where relevant). The DFA should thus address the limitations of the GDPR when it comes to preventing such exploitation of consumers and ensure that consumers have additional rights and mechanisms to safeguard their privacy when using digital and online services.

The consumer's privacy should not be degraded simply because they have been pestered with consent requests (also known as consent fatigue). Even if the consumer gives their consent, activities that enable mass collection of personal data are deeply invasive to the consumer's privacy, create an environment of surveillance, and ultimately impact the consumer's fundamental rights.

Recommendation 6.1.5: *The DFA should prohibit practices that represent mass (i.e. large-scale) violation of privacy. Such practices include the use of personal data of consumers for advertising carried out by multiple third parties that involves tracking or profiling, involves personal data without the consumer's knowledge or control over it, and thus prevents the consumer from correcting or rectifying it, and where the consumer is forced to reduce their privacy as part of accessing the service.*

6.2 Develop a technical framework to support privacy and consumer protection

Consumers are faced with too many decision making steps online that involve complex legal language and where there are no controls provided that act on behalf of consumers or act in their interests. To remedy this, consumer rights should be supported through technical means such as software settings and information management systems that can act on behalf of the consumer. However, when allowing such technical approaches to function, we are concerned that this might result in an increased violation of the individual's privacy as any mechanism used to justify collection and processing of personal data would carry risks of enabling this without the individual's consent. We therefore focus exclusively on supporting the consumer to prevent and halt harmful practices through technical means.

While here we focus only on the consumer's privacy with Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs), this approach has a broad application to consumer protection with existing examples of this in the US. Other examples include the "App Tracking Transparency (ATT)" signal present in iOS and other Apple devices which controls whether apps can ask the user to be tracked or not. The implementation of this is controlled solely by Apple. Without support from a regulatory obligation such as the DFA, such "protections" are threatened to be revoked at the whim of the company

providing them.⁵ We therefore urge the Commission to ensure such measures are obligations within the DFA.

In our submission to the consultation on omnibus,⁶ we have outlined specific criteria for "automated signals" to support the implementation of privacy protections for data subjects. Our submission also provides practical guidelines for the implementation of such automated signals for the ePrivacy Directive in terms of cookie banners and the complexities surrounding misuse of consent and legitimate interests under the GDPR. We recommend the DFA to implement similar measures in the context of consumer protection i.e. to support the implementation of consumer rights through technical solutions that are implemented at the device and application (e.g. web browser) levels.

To determine whether any technical solution should be legally accepted as an enforceable mechanism for consumer rights, it must have a recognition by both the service providers as well as authorities. When done at Member State or federal state levels, this creates fragmentation and gold plating, which are undesirable.⁷ To ensure consistency and harmonisation, decisions regarding acceptance of technical solutions for consumer protection must be adopted in a single and consistent manner across the EU. While for the GDPR this can be done through a harmonised decision by the EDPB as a representation of consensus amongst the GDPR authorities, no such body exists for the purposes of co-ordinating consumer rights.

Recommendation 6.2.1: *The DFA must establish an "European Consumer Protection Board", whose members must be the relevant consumer protection body within each Member State. The tasks of the board should include ensuring consistent application of the DFA across Member States, to settle conflicting interpretations through resolutions, and to support the implementation of consumer protection in practice through guidelines and the approval of technical solutions representing consumer's interests.*

6.3 Empower consumers to formulate their own contractual terms that are then enforced by their "digital agents"

Most of the terms accepted by consumers are of a standard form, are not negotiated by the consumers, and are written by a single party without the knowledge or

⁵ Apple threatens to drop 'Ask App Not to Track' privacy pop-ups in EU (2025) <https://www.euractiv.com/news/apple-threatens-to-drop-ask-app-not-to-track-privacy-pop-ups-in-eu/>

⁶ AIAL's Comments to the European Commission's "Simplification – Digital Package and Omnibus Consultation" (2025) AI Accountability Lab (AIAL). <https://aial.ie/research/policy/consultation-2025-EU-Digital-Omnibus-Simplification>

⁷ For example, in Germany we have the Consent Management Ordinance under the Telecommunications Digital Services Data Protection Act (TDDDG, 2024)

participation of the consumers. This allows the insertion of unfair terms within the contracts. In EU spheres surrounding law and policy, there is an increasing vision of changing this to provide the consumers with explicit power and ability to formulate, negotiate, and enforce their own contracts. Examples of this are MyData⁸ which aims to provide collaborative contracts for consumers and providers, Solid⁹ which is a vision by Tim Berners-Lee to create "pods" controlled by individuals with their data and which has seen a widespread adoption in Flanders, Belgium¹⁰, and the development of standards such as IEEE P7012¹¹ for machine-readable personal privacy terms (also called "MyTerms" where individuals have a first say in which contracts the service provider can use for their data. Such initiatives are currently working with the limitations in law regarding the ability of the individual consumer to unilaterally control and dictate their online experiences and contract formation. The DFA can support such initiatives by providing acknowledgement and guidelines for the implementation of contracts with the individual consumer as the first party i.e. the one drafting the contract and enforcing it digitally.

Recommendation 6.3.1: *The DFA should provide a separate set of obligations and rights for consumers to create and manage their own terms, such that service providers who accept such terms must abide by it and must not attempt to subvert or manipulate the consumer into accepting a different set of terms that are detrimental to their being.*

~ END ~

⁸ <https://mydata.org/>

⁹ <https://solidproject.org/>

¹⁰ <https://athumi.eu/>

¹¹ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7012/7192/>